

THE CONTENT OF PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL EXPERIMENTAL WORK IN THE LESSONS OF FINE ARTS, AND METHODS OF ITS ORGANIZATION

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In pedagogy - the concept of the person in psychology - in contrast to the concept of the person, it means the social characteristics of the person. The new society represents the qualities that are formed as a result of interaction with other people. Development of mental qualities of the person (mind, will, attention, action, etc.) level. The realization of these qualities depends on upbringing. But we must always remember that the concept of personality is a whole. In order to deeply understand a person's spiritual image, it is necessary not only to study his mental characteristics, but also to better understand his personality as a citizen, a public figure, an employee, and so on. In particular, it is impossible to study any particular mental process or individual trait (for example, observation, will, character, etc.) without linking it to the characteristics of a person's spiritual image in general. Getting to know someone is a very difficult task.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the concept of personality and the views expressed by educators and psychologists. Fine arts classes are about how to educate students and how to test their abilities and interests through experiments.

L. N. Tolstoy had a profound and good idea about it: —... I see you for the first time, your head, arms, legs are like all people, your face is the same or different. I see it, everyone sees it. But look, if I can find a way to your heart, I can put my hand on this place (he put his hand on my shoulder, he put his other hand on my chest), if he is there If I can make it clear, I can make people excited, I can make them cry, I can make them feel, I can make the invisible person look so clear, he otherwise I will be a true artist.

This is exactly what a psychologist or educator should do when he or she is learning about certain personality traits.

Everyone has an image, that is, he is a person, wrote the great Russian critic VG Belinsky, that everyone is in some way similar to other people and in some ways different from them. Everyone is unique.

When studying the social nature of a person's mental activity, it should always be borne in mind that a person's attitude towards the environment, other people,

and the individual depends on the characteristics of the society in which he or she lives. Everyone has a relationship with other members of the community. The same relationships shape a person's personality — a person learns the rules, customs, and norms of morality that are accepted and developed in that society, and acquires knowledge, skills, and work skills.

In adulthood, mental characteristics depend on the characteristics of the human nervous system, but the nervous system does not predetermine these mental characteristics, mental characteristics are not innate, they are related to biological characteristics. Man is not born with a ready character and interests, with ready inclinations, certain abilities, and so on. All of these qualities are formed gradually, in the process of life, and find content.

Upbringing plays a crucial role in a person's development. As a person grows mentally, self-education, that is, the conscious work of a person to improve his personal qualities, also plays an important role in the development of a person. For example, a person may set himself the task of developing his will, attention, memory, observation skills. To achieve this goal, a person performs certain exercises, overcomes obstacles, works hard, and thus achieves the desired results. Through self-discipline, many mental qualities can be greatly improved, and some personality flaws can be reduced.

Miracles can be achieved through hard work, perseverance, regular exercise, and hard work. At the same time, it is possible to self-educate and re-educate oneself in this environment. The work of improving one's level and skills always makes a person very happy and strengthens his will. The process of self-education and self-

improvement is most effective when it is strengthened by the educational influence of the family, school, or community. It is better if the goals and objectives of social education coincide with the personal goals and objectives of a person's self-education: then the personal thing and the social thing do not contradict each other, but will merge together. It would be great if young people could connect their personal happiness with the solution of social problems, for example, in order to become highly advanced builders of a communist society.

Looking at everyone with a superficial care, but with care and kindness, allows us to get to know and understand them better. In particular, a better understanding between the educator and the trainee will facilitate the achievement of the set goal and help to achieve good results. In this case, the trainee involuntarily helps his tutor, speeding up the process of developing the necessary mental qualities. However, it is very bad if the student is not interested in educational activities, especially if he does not understand the basics of such activities and resists them.

To be successful in parenting, you need to know the reasons behind your child's development. It is important to know the relationship between students at school, how child labor and leisure are organized, and much more. A student's life is based on all these relationships that need to be known, understood, and guided. Without this knowledge, it is impossible to talk seriously about educating, influencing, or educating oneself.

The importance of educational work lies in its effectiveness and practical results. Growing up is the process of composing a

person's socially significant actions and behaviors.

Community plays a particularly important role in nurturing an individual. The team is made up of a person's ideological orientation, his activities and behavior are regulated, the communist qualities of his character are cultivated, and the necessary conditions are created for the development of various abilities.

The team has a great opportunity to re-educate students and free them from the shackles of the past. However, while some people have some personality flaws and negative qualities, the reason for this is the insufficient use of the influence of the collective, community forces.

The educational impact of the team on its members depends on the ideological maturity, organization and cohesion of the team.

A person's goal is a complex mental concept that basically reflects a person's goals and aspirations. In order to get to know a person, it is necessary to know what motives and needs allow him to achieve these goals and aspirations, and what interests a person pursues in his behavior and activities in general. One is always satisfied with one's needs in the form of dissatisfaction or lack of something. People have different needs. There are material needs that directly enable a person to make a living: food, clothing, shelter, and so on. In addition to these needs, a person has spiritual needs - the need to communicate with other people, the need for work, cultural needs (reading books and newspapers, going to the theater, cinema, listening to the radio, watching television, etc.).

Human needs are the product of the socio-historical development of an individual's

society. In the process of this development, people's material and spiritual needs have become more and more complex and complex. expressed in aspiration.

There is a certain unity between needs and interests, and they are interconnected. A person's interests arise and are shaped by needs. Sustained interests and, in turn, sometimes new needs can be facilitated. This is how cultural needs arise from time to time in reading, music, art, sports, and so on.

There can be broad and narrow interests, deep and superficial interests, and in many ways these are the goals a person pursues. It is true that some people are characterized by a scattering of interests, in which case they have a clear goal. we say no

But a person is not limited to doing what he needs to do, and he is not content to do what he is interested in. A person's behavior is determined by spiritual motives, a sense of conscience, social duties, and so on.

Moral motives of human behavior are always expressed in spiritual ideals. Although there are occasional, there are people who do not have any moral principles. In this case, we are talking about an immoral person, whose obscenity is evident in his depraved behavior. Our society condemns and criticizes such people, and at the same time fights for their decency and personal dignity. A spiritual ideal is an example of a person's actions and behavior. Spiritual ideals are determined by one's worldview. Each historical period has its own ideals, the image of the ideal person, which embodies the most important qualities and goals of people.

Not only his past and life experience, but also his future, that is, the future of each person, is very important in shaping the spiritual image of a person, his spiritual integrity. Perspectives need to be considered when raising a person.

It is important for a teacher to be able to understand the psyche of his students, to have a deep and broad understanding of their temperament (client), character, habits, interests, hobbies, abilities. It is this perception and knowledge that is the result of psychological observation and ingenuity, which is an important skill of the educator.

A good teacher always knows his students, understands what is difficult for them, avoids difficulties and helps those who need help. He always treats his students fairly. Righteousness is a quality of a teacher, and students value it. Schoolchildren will never forgive their teacher's unfairness in assessing knowledge and behavior. They think that the worst teacher is the one who is unfair.

A good teacher develops a good experience according to his or her circumstances. The creativity of a teacher is manifested in ingenuity, in finding different ways of teaching. A teacher who shows great creative initiative and is not only knowledgeable but also able to do a lot with his own hands will always attract the love of students and be a role model.

Pedagogical etiquette is an important quality of an advanced teacher's personality.

It is important for a teacher to be confident at all times and in all circumstances. The teacher's responsiveness, ability to act immediately in a given situation, and ability to decide how to behave in a situation are important.

Teaching requires good organizational skills, the ability to manage a team of students, the ability to lead their work. A teacher's ability to organize is first and foremost a matter of how well he or she conducts the lesson: it is both a well-planned lesson and a clear plan.

Accurate, fluent, cultural speech is very important in a teacher's educational work. In addition, the teacher's speech should be distinguished by certain qualities that make his speech pedagogical. It's a speech that addresses a specific issue. Whether the teacher explains new tasks, checks their performance, tries to convince children of something, approves or criticizes something, in all cases the speech of a qualified teacher is characterized by activity, enthusiasm and sincerity, confidence in what is being said. That's why a teacher's speech is so effective. Mastering the intonation of speech is also important for the teacher.

In an ideal teacher, the qualities of a very good teacher and a very good educator are combined.

One of the important methodological problems of the pedagogical course is the problem of upbringing and development of the individual.

A person who grows and develops is an object of education. Throughout his life, a person continues to develop. In the process, he undergoes various changes, physical, mental, quantitative and qualitative. Physical changes include height gain, weight gain, and changes in the musculoskeletal system, internal organs, and nervous system. Mental changes, on the other hand, are related to a person's mental development and the formation of an individual's mental qualities, including the social qualities necessary for life.

The development of the human child is an important process. It is well-known that a person changes physically and mentally throughout his life. But in childhood, adolescence and adolescence, development is extremely powerful. During these years, the child develops as a person due to both physical and mental growth and change, and as a result of the purposeful influence of the upbringing, the child develops as a member of society and fits into a complex system of social relations. takes place.

What factors influence a child's development, psyche, and character development? Pedagogy says that a child's upbringing, its formation is influenced by biological factors, social factors and upbringing. This is a problem that has long been debated in pedagogy.

In the course of this centuries of debate, two opposing views have emerged. Some of them believe that natural biological factors play a crucial role in the development of the human child. According to them, a child develops only innate traits that are passed down from generation to generation during the mother's womb. Proponents of this view limit the role of education. This view is called the biological direction in science. Their representative, Aristotle, according to Plato, predestined the place and fate of everyone in life.

From infancy, the human child acquires all the characteristics of the future personality, and development is the quantitative increase of these characteristics. Preformists also overestimate the role of generation in personal development and categorically deny the role of social environment and upbringing. Another aspect of this theory was the widespread behaviorism of the twentieth century.

Behaviorism was founded by American educator and psychologist E. Torandaik. According to him, all the characteristics of a person, including the mind and mental abilities, are passed down from generation to generation. In this way, E. Torandaik denies the influence of upbringing on the development of the individual, considering it incapable of influencing the characteristics of the individual.

Faroobi and Abu Ali ibn Sina, two Central Asian thinkers, also emphasized the importance of factors influencing personal development. Emphasizing the importance of education in the development of a person, Farobi said: "To be a decent person, a person has two opportunities: education and upbringing. "Through education, theoretical maturity is achieved, and education is a way to build moral dignity and practical action in communicating with people."

Abu Ali ibn Sina tries to cover the issues of ethics and moral education on a philosophical and pedagogical basis. He emphasized the role of parents, especially in family upbringing: - When a child is born, first of all, the father should give him a good name, and then bring him up well ... If the family uses good methods of upbringing, the family promotes the idea that one will be happy.

Factors such as heredity, environment, and upbringing influence a child's personal development. It is important to understand that the influence of offspring on the development of a child's personality is the repetition of biological traits that represent parental similarity. Every child is born with certain biological traits (body structure, hair, eyes, skin color, height, etc.) inherited from their parents. These are physical features. Features of high nervous activity

are also congenital. This is a physiological feature.

If a child grows up in the right environment and engages in the necessary activities, the ability will appear and develop early, otherwise it may disappear. Therefore, pedagogy believes that the manifestation and development of abilities depends entirely on living conditions and upbringing.

One of the factors influencing the development of a person is the environment, which is a complex of external events that affect a person spontaneously. This includes the natural environment, the social environment, the family environment (microenvironment).

The natural (geographical) environment (climate, natural conditions and wealth) inevitably affects a person's lifestyle, character and work activities. For example, the lifestyles of individuals living in the tropics are different from those of people in the far north, as evidenced by a number of factors that affect their lifestyles and their development.

At the same time, the microenvironment - the family environment - has a great influence on the development of the individual. Because when a child opens his eyes, he sees his parents and relatives. His period of intensive physical and psychological development is formed under the influence of the family, and in our people - the saying "he does what he sees in the bird's nest" is not in vain. The lifestyle of the family, the educational environment that has a positive impact on the upbringing of the child, plays an important role in its development.

The social environment is important in the development of the child. Because here the relations of production and the social laws

that regulate them have a special effect on a person. Without social contact, without contact with people, one cannot be a person. As a result of this kind of attitude, the human child is prepared for life and work, acquires the necessary experience and knowledge.

The influence of the social environment on the development of the individual varies in different historical periods (formations), and also affects different social groups. Therefore, modern pedagogy pays special attention to the environment and the role of its impact on personal development. The influence of social life events on the individual, which is part of the concept of environment, is very important, and the social environment is considered to be changeable, not eternal. Therefore, the environment is not considered a factor that determines a person's destiny. But he does not deny its influence.

But the strength of the influence of upbringing and its outcome is determined by a combination of factors such as heredity and environment.

A person's maturity is determined not only by heredity and natural abilities, but also by the qualities and attributes he has acquired under the influence of the reality that surrounds him throughout his life.

Of course, upbringing does not affect a person's eyes, hair, skin color, or body composition. But it can also affect your physical development. Because the health of the child is strengthened and strengthened through specially organized exercise. It is well-known that a person's natural ability can be developed only through upbringing, by involving him in a certain type of activity.

It is well-known that the development of a child's abilities requires diligence and

diligence in order to turn them into abilities and bring them up in accordance with life. Qualities such as hard work and constant sitting are qualities that can only be acquired through training. Although there are a number of factors that affect a person's maturity, the educational process under the guidance of a tutor in special educational institutions is the leading one. Because, first of all, under the influence of upbringing, the qualities that can not be influenced by the environment are mastered and things are studied, that is, knowledge, information is acquired, skills related to labor and technical activity, skills are also specially organized is formed through education.

Second, upbringing can help to change a person's imperfections. For example, the blind and the deaf are educated and prepared for life as healthy people.

Third, with the help of education, the negative effects of the environment can be eliminated or eliminated.

Fourth, education always sets goals for the future. As a result, it plays a role in accelerating the development of the individual. School plays an important role in the development of a person. As children enter school, they become more involved in their studies. As children acquire the basics of science at school, they gradually develop a scientific outlook. Under the guidance of teachers, they acquire high personal qualities. She always helps the family in

raising the child by organizing the educational work according to the plan. It is important for the educator to be aware of the child's family situation, to provide pedagogical advice, and to help families in need. It doesn't matter to the educator who the child spends his free time with and what he does. Because an abandoned child can be exposed to the negative effects of the street.

In conclusion, the diagnosis of talent is a topical and complex issue for many professionals, educators and psychologists. This is due to many reasons, such as the diversity of talents, the psychological characteristics of the child (shyness, anxiety, low self-esteem, stress, lack of confidence in the psychological test), the qualifications of the specialist. There are many psychological ways to identify talent. These include methods such as observation, conversation, creativity, ability, motivation, personal characteristics. Often, this diversity complicates the process of identifying talent.

It is obvious that the correct organization of lessons leads to high results in building the capacity of gifted students, as well as the need to select additional gifted students, which is the subject of our study, and to organize additional clubs for students. It is interesting and understandable to teach a lesson using today's technology.

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